

Studies on Sigmatropic Rearrangements : Regioselective Synthesis of Coumarins, Quinolones and Thiocoumarins with 3,4-Fused Pyran or Furan Ring Systems by Claisen Rearrangement

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A brief review of the regioselective synthesis of pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-ones, pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-one, pyrano[3,2-c]quinolin-5(2*H*)-ones, pyrano[2,3-c][1]benzopyran-5(3*H*)-ones, 3*H*-pyrano[2,3-c]quinolin-5(6*H*)-ones, thiapyrano[2,3-*b*][1]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-ones, thiapyrano[2,3-*b*][1]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-ones, furo[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-4-ones, furo[3,2-c]quinolin-4(5*H*)-ones, furo[3,2-c][1]benzothiapyran-4-one, furo[2,3-c][1]benzopyran-4-ones, furo[2,3-c]quinolin-4(5*H*)-ones and thieno[2,3-*b*][1]benzothiapyran-4-one by the application of the Claisen rearrangement is presented. This also includes 3,4-fused pyran or furan rings forming the part of polycyclic systems.

Pyran and furan rings are found in many naturally occurring compounds including pyran and furan rings fused in heterocyclic compounds like coumarins¹, quinolones² etc. Sigmatropic rearrangements especially Claisen rearrangement³ has been widely used for the construction of the pyran and furan rings, e.g. benzopyran and 2-methylbenzofuran⁴. Coumarin and its derivatives are biologically active⁵ and 3-alkyl- and 4-alkylcoumarins are known to possess various physiological activities⁶. Formation of the pyran and furan rings fused in the benzenoid part of heterocycles by Claisen rearrangement has already been reviewed⁷. We undertook a study to generate pyran ring and furan ring at the 3,4-position of the coumarin and related heterocyclic systems by Claisen rearrangement. A brief account of our recent work on the synthesis of pyrano- and furoheterocycles derived from 3-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxycoumarin (1 and 2) as well as from other related heterocycles, such as 3-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxyquinolone (3 and 4), 4-hydroxythiocoumarin (5), and 4-hydroxydithiocoumarin (6) is presented here. Pyran or furan forming the part of related polycyclic heterocycles has also been included. No attempt has been made to include comprehensive tables covering all known pyrano- and furo-3,4-fused heterocycles in this brief account.

Synthesis of pyrano- and furoheterocycles

The pyrano- and furoheterocycles are easily accessible

from the thermal sigmatropic rearrangement of alkynyl and alkenyl ethers respectively of the corresponding hydroxyheterocycles. The required ethers are easily prepared from the hydroxyheterocycles, e.g. 4-hydroxy- and 3-hydroxycoumarin (1 and 2), 4-hydroxy- and 3-hydroxyquinolone (3 and 4), 4-hydroxythiocoumarin (5) and 4-hydroxydithiocoumarin (6) by their reaction with alkynyl or alkenyl halides in acetone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate⁸ or in the presence of a phase transfer catalyst⁹.

Pyranoheterocycles :

Pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-ones, pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-ones and pyrano[3,2-c]quinolin-5(2*H*)-ones : The ether, 4-propargyloxycoumarin (7) was heated in chlorobenzene at 100° to give the 3,4-fused pyranocoumarin^{8a}, viz. pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-one (11) (Scheme 1). This method has also been utilized for the

Scheme 1

regioselective synthesis¹⁰ of a number of pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-one derivatives (12) starting from 1-aryloxy-4-(4-coumarinyloxy)but-2-yne (8, R = CH₂OAr) Regioselective synthesis of pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-one¹¹ (13) has been achieved similarly from the

propargyl ether of 4-hydroxythiocoumarin (9).

Flindersine, 2,2-dimethylpyrano[3,2-*c*]quinolin-5(2*H*)-one (14) and various substituted flindersine derivatives are widely distributed in nature¹². A good deal of work has been reported on the synthesis of flindersine¹³ and its analogs with various substitution in the aromatic ring. A simple methodology for the regioselective synthesis of flindersine analogs, pyrano[3,2-*c*]quinolin-5(2*H*)-ones (15) with variation in the dihydropyran ring has recently been reported¹⁴ (Scheme 1) by the thermolysis of 4-propargyloxyquinolin-2(1*H*)-one. This method is perhaps the simplest route for the synthesis of these heterocycles.

The butyne derivative containing aryloxy moiety carrying a methyl group at the *para*-position (8*m*) afforded the normal pyranocoumarin along with its isomer (16*m*). The one with methyl group at the *ortho*-position (8*n*) also gave the normal pyranocoumarin¹⁵ with its isomer (17*n*) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The 4-aryloxymethylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-ones (12) still contain allyl ether moiety, a potential site for a further sigmatropic rearrangement. These compounds indeed underwent a second Claisen rearrangement to give¹⁶ 3-(hydroxyphenyl)-4-methylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5(4*H*)-ones (18) (Scheme 3).

Another synthesis of pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-one (11) along with 2-methylfuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (20) has been reported¹⁷ from the reaction of 3-allylcoumarin-4-oxyanion (19) with palladium chloride-bisbenzonitrile (Scheme 4).

*Pyrano[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-5(3*H*)-ones and 3*H*-pyranof[2,3-*c*]quinolin-5(6*H*)-ones*: These are also regioselectively synthesized by the thermal sigmatropic rearrangement of propargyl ethers of 3-hydroxycoumarin. 3-Propargyloxycoumarin (21) on heating in chlorobenzene at 100° furnished^{8a} the title compound, pyrano[2,3-*c*][1]ben-

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

zopyran-5(3*H*)-one (27, R = H) (Scheme 5). A regioselective synthesis of pyrano[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-5(3*H*)-one derivatives has been achieved via the pericyclic pathway. If ionic or radical pathway is allowed to follow then the corresponding furo[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one derivatives are obtained^{18,19}. 1-Aryloxy-4-coumarin-3-yloxybut-2-yne (22) in refluxing chlorobenzene (132°) underwent an initial [3*s*,3*s*]-sigmatropic rearrangement to give the allenlenols (26). In absence of any other agents (acid, base or radical initiator) normally the pericyclic pathway is followed to give the 1-aryloxymethylpyrano[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-5(3*H*)-ones (28) in almost quantitative yields. This reaction when conducted in commercial chlorobenzene without further purification, a mixture of furo- and

Scheme 5

pyranocoumarins are obtained. The products are well-characterized by the application of modern spectroscopic methods, e.g. high resolution ^1H nmr and ^{13}C nmr spectra²⁰.

The same methodology has been successfully utilized²¹ for the regioselective synthesis of 3*H*-pyrano[2,3-*c*]quinolin-5(6*H*)-one (29). The propargyl ethers on refluxing in chlorobenzene gave a number of 3*H*-pyrano[2,3-*c*]quinolin-5(6*H*)-ones (29) in almost quantitative yields (Scheme 5). While 3-propargyloxy ethers (23) gave exclusively the pyranoquinolones (29), the 3-(4-aryloxybut-2-ynyl)-1-methylquinolin-2-ones (24, R = CH₂OAr) in refluxing chlorobenzene generated²² pyranoquinolone (30) or furoquinolones (31) or a mixture of both. Recently, a synthesis of 1-methylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5(3*H*)-one (27, R = CH₃) has been reported. 4-(2-Methylallyl)-3-hydroxycoumarin on treatment with PdCl₂(CH₃CN)₂ furnished the pyranocoumarin (27, R = CH₃). General regio-selectivity has not been achieved²³. 4-Allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin gave only 2-methylfuro[2,3-*c*]coumarin in 40% yield. Most of the other substrates studied gave mixture of two products.

Thiapyrano[2,3-*b*]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-ones and thiapyrano[2,3-*b*]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-ones : Initial efforts towards the synthesis of pyrano[3,2-*c*]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-thione failed, and instead thiapyrano[2,3-*b*]benzothiapyran-5(4*H*)-one (32) and thiapyrano[2,3-*b*]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-ones (33 and 34) were obtained^{24,25} from the phase transfer catalyzed reaction of 4-hydroxydithiocoumarin (6) and propargyl bromides in CH₂Cl₂-1% aq. NaOH in the presence of tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) or benzyl triethylammonium chloride (BTEAC) (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

A number of thiapyrano[2,3-*b*]benzothiapyran-5(2*H*)-one derivatives (37) have been synthesized²⁶ by the thermal thio-Claisen rearrangement of the sulphides (35) obtained from the phase transfer catalyzed reaction of 4-hydroxydithiocoumarin (6) and 1-aryloxy-4-chlorobut-2-ynes. The same methodology has also been applied for the regioselective synthesis of a number of hitherto unreported²⁷ thiapyrano[2,3-*b*]benzopyran-5(2*H*)-ones (38) from 4-

propargyloxy[1]benzopyran-2-thione (36) obtained from thionation of the 4-propargyloxy coumarin (7) (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Furoheterocycles :

Furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-ones, furo[3,2-*c*]quinolin-4(5*H*)-ones and furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzothiapyran-4-ones : 2,3-Dihydrofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one has been reported²⁸ which can be dehydrogenated to furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (44). The synthesis of furo[3,2-*c*]benzothiapyran-4-one¹¹ (45) and furo[3,2-*c*]quinolin-4(5*H*)-one^{8b} (46) by the thermal sigmatropic rearrangement of allyl ethers of 4-hydroxythiocoumarin (5) and 4-hydroxyquinolin-2(1*H*)-one (3) respectively, followed by acid-catalyzed cyclization and dehydrogenation has been reported. The recent trend is to use the chloropropenyl ethers of 4-hydroxycoumarin^{8b} (1), 4-hydroxythiocoumarin¹¹ (5), and 4-hydroxyquinolone³⁰ (3) instead of the allyl ether of the hydroxy heterocycles (Scheme 8). Furo[3,2-*c*]quinolin-4(5*H*)-one (46) derivatives have also been synthesized³⁰ by

Scheme 8

simply refluxing 1-alkyl-4-hydroxyquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones with a number of acetylenic halides in 1-butanol in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. 4-Propargyloxy coumarin (7) underwent extensive decomposition^{8b} when heated in *N,N*-dimethylaniline at 100°.

A recent report, although related but not via sigmatropic rearrangement, describes the synthesis of furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one³¹ (44, R = H) from 4-hydroxycoumarin (1) and chloroacetaldehyde in the presence of aqueous hydrochloric acid. This seems to be the simplest synthesis for this heterocycle devoid of any substitution on the

furan ring. This methodology has also been applied to the synthesis of furo[3,2-*c*]quinolone (**46**, R = H) devoid of any substitution of the furan ring.

Recently, Bohlmann and Steinmeyer³² reported the synthesis of natural cyclobrachycoumarin (**48**) isolated from *Brachyclados* species by the abnormal Claisen rearrangement of 4-geranyloxy-5-methylcoumarin (**47**) (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Furo[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-ones and *furo*[2,3-*c*]quinolin-4(5*H*)-ones : A number of 2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (**49**) derivatives have been reported³³ from thermal [3s,3s]-sigmatropic rearrangement of ethers of 3-hydroxycoumarin followed by acid-catalyzed cyclization. The 2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (**49**) has been dehydrogenated to **50** (R = H). This heterocycle (**50**, R = H) has also been synthesized²⁹ by [3s,3s]-sigmatropic rearrangement of 3-chloropropenyloxycoumarin followed by acid-catalyzed cyclization^{8b}. This was also obtained^{8b} by the thermal rearrangement of 3-propargyloxycoumarin (**21**) in dimethylaniline at 100°. Recently it has been demonstrated¹⁸ that the intermediate allenyl enols (**26**) from the thermal [3s,3s]-sigmatropic rearrangement of 3-(4-aryloxybut-2-ynyloxy)coumarins (**22**) may be cyclized following a radical as well as an ionic pathway to give 1-aryloxy-2-methylfuro[2,3-*c*][1]benzopyran-4(*H*)-ones (**50**) (Scheme 10).

Furo[2,3-*c*]quinolin-4(5*H*)-ones (**31**, R = H) have also been synthesized by the thermal rearrangement²¹ of 3-allyloxyquinolone followed by acid-catalyzed cyclization and subsequent dehydrogenation or by the thermal rearrangement of 3-[2-chloropropenyloxy]quinolone followed by cyclization with conc. H₂SO₄ or heterocycles of the type **31** (R = CH₂OAr) by the thermal rearrangement of 3-(4-aryloxybut-2-ynyloxy)quinolin-2(1*H*)-ones²² (**24**) in the presence of toluene-4-sulphonic acid. Interestingly, 1-aryloxymethyl-3*H*-pyrano[2,3-*c*]quinolin-5(6*H*)-ones (**30**) on heating in refluxing *N,N*-diethylaniline afforded 1-

Scheme 10

aryloxymethyl-2-methylfuro[2,3-*c*]quinolin-4(5*H*)-ones (**31**, R = CH₂OAr) by the reversal of electrocyclic ring closure and [1,5]H shift steps followed by base-catalyzed cyclization³⁴.

Thieno[2,3-*b*][1]benzothiapyran-4-ones : Attempts to synthesize furo[3,2-*c*]benzothiapyran-4-thione were of no avail. Alkylation of 4-hydroxydithiocoumarin (**6**) with allyl halides either by classical method or by phase transfer catalyzed condition gave exclusively 2-alkylthiobenzothiapyran-4(*H*)-thione in almost quantitative yields²⁵. Reaction of 4-hydroxydithiocoumarin (**6**) with allyl bromide using Mitsunobu reaction condition also failed to give any O-ether, instead 2-allylthiobenzothiapyran-4(*H*)-thione¹⁷ was obtained. However, 4-hydroxydithiocoumarin (**6**) with propargyl bromide, 3-bromobut-1-yne and 3-chloro-3-methylbut-1-yne afforded 2-alkylthieno[2,3-*b*][1]benzothiapyran-4(*H*)-ones (**51-53**) when refluxed in acetone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (Scheme 11). Reaction of **6** with allyl bromide under similar condition gave 2,3-dihydro-2-methylthieno[2,3-*b*][1]benzothiapyran-4(*H*)-one which on dehydrogenation furnished the thieno[2,3-*b*][thiachromone (**51**).

3,4-Fused pyran or furan rings part of a polycyclic system

Recently some work has been reported on the synthesis of polyheterocycles derived from the product of Claisen rearrangement of allyl (cyclohexenyl or cyclopentenyl) ethers

Scheme 11

of 3-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxycoumarin, 3-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxyquinolone. The allylenol substrates (54-59) have been utilized for the synthesis of polyheterocycles containing pyran or furan ring.

Three different approaches were made for the generation of the pyran or the furan ring in the resulting polyheterocycles : (i) 'approach A_a' - conversion of the allylenol to acetate to dibromoacetate followed by cyclization with alcoholic alkali³⁵; 'approach A_b' - reaction of the 2-allylenol with pyridine hydrotribromide³⁶ or hexamethylenetetramine hydrotribromide³⁷, (ii) 'approach B' - reaction of the 2-allylenol with Hg(OAc)₂ in methanol³⁸ and demercuration of the resulting mercurated cyclic product and (iii) 'approach C' - acid-catalyzed cyclization of the 2-allylenol³⁹.

Polyheterocycles through 'approach A' :

4-Cyclohex-2-enyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (54) and 4-cyclohex-2-enyl-3-hydroxy-1-methylquinolin-2(1H)-one (56) through sequence of reactions 'approach A_a' gave the bicyclic compounds^{40,41} with the pyran ring (60 and 61), whereas reaction of 56 with pyridine hydrotribromide or hexamethylenetetramine hydrotribromide (approach A_b) afforded the linear furo derivative⁴² (62) in almost quantitative yields (Scheme 12).

Scheme 12

4-Cyclohex-2-enyl-3-hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-one (58) via 'approach A_a' also gave the bicyclic pyranocoumarin derivative⁴³ (63). 3-Cyclohex-2-enyl-4-hydroxy-1-methylquinolin-2(1H)-one (57) through 'approach A_a' gave the bicyclic pyranoquinolone (64), while through 'approach A_b' furnished the linear furoquinolone⁴⁴ (65). 3-Cyclohex-2-enyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (55) through 'approach A_a' gave

a poor yield of the bicyclic compound (66), a chromone instead of the coumarin⁴¹.

3-Cyclohex-2-enyl-4-hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-one (59) on treatment with pyridine hydrotribromide in dichloromethane (approach A_b) provided a linear furochromone (67) which underwent an interesting acid-catalyzed rearrangement⁴⁵ to afford furocoumarin (68) (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

Polyheterocycles through 'approach B' :

3-Cyclohex-2-enyl-4-hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-one (55) has been cyclized⁴¹ by the application of well-known

oxymercuration reaction. The resulting cyclized product (69) was converted to benzofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-6-one (70) by dehydrogenative demercuration with Pd-C in refluxing diphenyl ether (Scheme 14).

Scheme 14

4-Cyclohex-2-enyl-3-hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-one (54) underwent similar oxymercuration-demercuration⁴⁰ to give benzofuro[2,3-*c*]benzopyran-6-one (71). 4-Cyclopent-2-enyl-3-hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-one (58) also underwent oxymercuration⁴³ but the oxymercurred cyclized product gave back the substrate (58) on treatment with Pd-C in diphenyl ether or NaBH₄ in aqueous ethanol. The demercuration was finally achieved⁴³ with Zn(BH₄)₂ in dimethoxyethane to give 72.

71

72

Polyheterocycles through 'approach C' :

Cyclization of 4-cyclohex-2-enyl-3-hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-one (54) and 4-cyclohex-2-enyl-3-hydroxy-1-methylquinolin-2(1*H*)-one (56) has been effected^{40,42} with cold conc. sulphuric acid to give bicyclic pyranoheterocycles 73 and 74. 3-Cyclohex-2-enyl-4-hydroxy[1]benzo-

73, X = O

74, X = NMe

75

76

77

78

pyran-2-one (55) on similar treatment furnished⁴¹ a mixture of 75 and 76. Reaction of 4-cyclopent-2-enyl-3-hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-one (58) with H₂SO₄ also generated a mixture⁴³ of 77 and 78.

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References

1. R. D. H. MURRAY, *Natural Prod. Rep.*, 1989, 600.
2. (a) L. JURD and M. J. BENSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1983, 92; (b) J. REISCH, J. KOROSI, K. SZENDREI, I. NOVAK, and E. MINKER, *Phytochemistry*, 1975, 14, 1678.
3. (a) R. P. LUTZ, *Chem. Rev.*, 1984, 84, 205; (b) G. B. BENNET, *Synthesis*, 1977, 589.
4. N. SARCEVIC, J. ZSINDELY, and H. SCHMID, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 56, 1457.
5. G. FEUR in "Progress in Medicinal Chemistry", eds. G. P. ELLIS and G. B. WEST, North Holland Publishing, New York, 1974.
6. VON P. LAUGER, H. MARTIN, and P. MULLER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 892; (b) H. KITAGAWA, R. IWAKI, B. YANAGI, and T. SATO, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Jpn.)*, 1956, 76, 186; (c) T. O. SOINE, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, 53, 231; (d) F. M. DEAN, "Naturally Occurring Oxygen Ring Compounds", Butterworths, London, 1963; (e) K. P. LINK, *Federation Proc.*, 1945, 4, 176; (f) P. MEUNIER, C. MENTZER, and M. A. VINET, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 1291; (g) A. A. DEANA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1983, 26, 580.
7. C. J. MOODY, *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1987, 42, 203.
8. (a) K. C. MAJUMDAR, R. N. DE, and A. T. KHAN, *Synth. Commun.*, 1988, 18, 1589; (b) K. C. MAJUMDAR, D. P. DAS, and A. T. KHAN, *Synth. Commun.*, 1989, 19, 917.
9. (a) K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. T. KHAN, and S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, *Heterocycles*, 1989, 29, 1573; (b), *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, 29, 483.
10. K. C. MAJUMDAR, D. P. DAS, and A. T. KHAN, *Synth. Commun.*, 1988, 18, 2027.
11. K. C. MAJUMDAR, P. K. CHOUDHURY, and A. T. KHAN, *Synth. Commun.*, 1989, 19, 3249.
12. (a) R. F. C. BROWN, J. J. HOBBS, G. K. HUGHES, and E. RITCHIE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1954, 7, 348; (b) R. F. C. BROWN, G. K. HUGHES, and E. RITCHIE, *Chem. Ind.*, 1955, 1385; (c) D. LAVIE, N. DANIELI, R. WEITMAN, and E. GLOTTER, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, 24, 3011; (d) D. L. DREYER and A. LEE, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, 11, 763; (e) D. R. TAYLOR and J. M. WARNER, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, 12, 1359; (f) J. REISCH, J. KOROSI, K. SZENDREI, I. NOVAK, and E. MINKER, *Phytochemistry*, 1975, 14, 1678.
13. (a) J. W. HUFFMAN and T. M. HSU, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1972, 141; (b) F. PIOZZI, P. VENTURELLA, and A. BELLINO, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1969, 99, 711; (c) A. GROOT and B. J. M. JANSEU, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 3407; (d) R. M. BOWMAN, M. F. GRUNDON, and K. J. JAMES, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1973, 1055; (e) M. RAMESH, P. S. MOHAN, and P. SHANMUGAM, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, 40, 4041; (f) M. F. GRUNDON, D. M. HARRISON, M. G. MAGEE, M. J. RUTHERFORD, and S. A. SURGENOR, *Proc. R. Ir. Acad. (B)*, 1983, 83, 103; (g) J. REISCH, A. BATHE, B. H. W. ROSENTHAL, A. SALAH, and A. J. REZA, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1987, 24, 869.

14. K. C. MAJUMDAR and P. K. CHOUDHURY, *Synth. Commun.*, 1993, **23**, 1087.
15. K. C. MAJUMDAR, D. P. DAS, G. H. JANA, and A. T. KHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, **33**, 120.
16. K. C. MAJUMDAR, D. P. DAS, and G. H. JANA, *Synth. Commun.*, 1993, **23**, 2171.
17. R. J. KUMAR, G. L. KRUPADANAM, and G. SRIMANARAYAN, *Synthesis*, 1990, 535.
18. K. C. MAJUMDAR and R. N. DE, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1989, 1901.
19. K. C. MAJUMDAR, R. N. DE, A. T. KHAN, S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, K. DEY, and A. PATRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem Commun.*, 1988, 777.
20. A. PATRA, S. K. PANDA, K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. T. KHAN, and S. SAHA, *Magn Reson. Chem.*, 1991, **28**, 631.
21. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. K. KUNDU, and P. CHATTERJEE, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1995, 386; *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 1995, 2301.
22. K. C. MAJUMDAR and A. K. KUNDU, *Heterocycles*, 1997, **45**, 1467.
23. J. MITRA and A. K. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, **33**, 273.
24. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. T. KHAN, and S. SAHA, *Synlett.*, 1991, 595.
25. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. T. KHAN, and S. SAHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, **30**, 643.
26. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. T. KHAN, and S. SAHA, *Synth. Commun.*, 1992, **22**, 901.
27. K. C. MAJUMDAR and G. H. JANA, *Heterocycles*, 1996, **43**, 767.
28. (a) R. R. SHAH and K. N. TRIVEDI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 226; (b) A. PATRA and A. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 1167.
29. TH. KAPPE, P. F. FRITZ, and E. ZIEGLER, *Chem Ber.*, 1973, **106**, 1927.
30. (a) K. C. MAJUMDAR and P. K. CHOUDHURY, *Heterocycles*, 1991, **32**, 73; (b) S. V. RAO and M. DARBARWAR, *Synthesis*, 1989, 139.
31. K. C. MAJUMDAR and T. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1997, 244; *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 1997, 1701.
32. F. BOHLMAN and A. STEINMEYER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 5329.
33. (a) A. PATRA, A. MUKHOPADHYAY, and A. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 834; A. K. MITRA, A. K. MUKHOPADHYAY, S. K. MISRA, and A. PATRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 834; (b) A. G. GONZALEZ, Z. D. JORGE, and L. F. RODRIGUEZ, *Ann. Quim., Ser. C*, 1983, **79**, 199 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1985, **102**, 5998); (c) V. K. AHLUWALIYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, **17**, 395; (d) R. R. SHAH and K. N. TRIVEDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 210.
34. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. K. KUNDU, and P. BISWAS, unpublished results.
35. (a) R. GAERTNER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4400; (b) K. C. MAJUMDAR and B. K. SEN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 1184; (c) K. C. MAJUMDAR, S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, and B. K. SEN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 56; (d) K. C. MAJUMDAR, S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, and R. N. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, **26**, 480.
36. (a) K. C. MAJUMDAR and A. K. KUNDU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1993, **32**, 605; (b) *Can. J. Chem.*, 1995, **73**, 1727.
37. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. K. KUNDU, and P. CHATTERJEE, *Synth. Commun.*, 1996, **26**, 893.
38. T. HOSOKAWA, S. MIYAGI, S. MURAHASHI, A. SONODA, Y. MATSUURA, S. TANIMOTO, and M. KAKUDO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 719.
39. (a) J. W. CORNFORTH, G. K. HUGHES, and F. LIONS, *Proc. R. Soc. NS Wales*, 1938, **71**, 323; (b) C. D. HURD and W. A. HOFFMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, **5**, 212; (c) GY. FRATER and H. SCHMID, *Helv Chim. Acta*, 1967, **50**, 255.
40. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. T. KHAN, A. K. GUPTA, and K. DEY, *Synth. Commun.*, 1990, **20**, 1249.
41. K. C. MAJUMDAR, A. T. KHAN, A. K. GUPTA, and P. K. CHOUDHURY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 667.
42. K. C. MAJUMDAR and A. K. KUNDU, *Synth. Commun.*, 1996, **26**, 4023.
43. K. C. MAJUMDAR and P. K. CHOUDHURY, *Synth. Commun.*, 1992, **22**, 3013.
44. K. C. MAJUMDAR and T. BHATTACHARYYA, unpublished results.
45. K. C. MAJUMDAR, P. K. CHOUDHURY, and M. NETHAJI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **35**, 5927.